

Studies on the Parental Attitude towards Female Child Education in Gashu'a Local Government Area Yobe State

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Abstract

The study was designed to investigate parental attitude toward female child education in Gashu'a local Government area of yobe state. 50 questionnaires were distributed to the respondent across the study areas. The researchers employed simple random sampling technique to select the sample for the research. The result shows majority of the respondent agreed that the education of women is of paramount importance to the society as against the traditional notion that girls should remain in the kitchen. The researchers recommended that Government should provide incentives for girls in order to attract them into teaching profession. The ministry of education at all level of Government should strengthen its policy that prohibits parents from withdrawing their children from schools for the sake of marriage.

Keywords: Parent, Women, Attitude, Education, Government, Society, Belief.

INTRODUCTION

In Africa, women are considered as men's properties or pleasure objects. They are also considered as a 'machine' meant for producing children. These situations have resulted in unfair treatment of women especially with regards to education of the male-child than the female child. In the traditional Nigerian society, there exist the believe that women are second class citizen (Enejere, 1991). The author further avers that gender inequality in Nigeria is promoted by religious and communal customs. Young girls particularly in Northern Nigeria are denied the benefit of education. This has given consequences for both the individual and the society at large.

Obinaju (2014) sees education as inalienable right of all irrespective of the person's circumstance.

Education in its general sense is a form of learning which the knowledge, skills, values, benefits and habits of a group of people are transferred from one generation to the next through storytelling, discussion, teaching, training or research. Education has been described as the most important aspect of human development, a key to a successful living, especially girl-child education (Micheal, 2011).

Girl-child education is a catch-all term for a complex set of issues and debates surrounding (primary education, secondary, and tertiary and health education in particular) for girl and women. Denying the girl-child access to education implies making her a dysfunctional member of the society. Statistics show that many girls are not enrolled in school. The global figure for out of school children is estimated at 121 million, 65 million are girls with over 80 percent of these girls in sub-sahara Africa including Nigeria (UNICEF, 2007).

The concern of this paper is that despite the campaign by the Federal Government, United Nation Children Education Fund (UNICEF) and stakeholder in education to improve girl-child education in Nigeria, the level of discrimination on girl-child education is still high. Therefore, this paper seeks to redress the challenges that negate the effectiveness of girl-child education in Nigeria.

Within the context of education, many scholars have defined girl-child education in various ways. The National Child Welfare Policy (1989) as cited by Ada (2007) defines girl-child as a person below 14 years of age. Offorma (2009) defines girl-child as a biological female offspring from birth to eighteen (18) years of age. This period is made up of infancy, childhood, early and late adolescence stage of development. The girl-child is seen as a young female person, who would eventually grow into women and marry. She is conditional to look after the young ones the home and kitchen.

Girl-child education is a catch-all term for a complexity of issues and debates surrounding education (primary education, secondary education, tertiary education and health education for females (Okernmor, Ndit and Filshak, 2012). Girl-child education also includes areas of gender equality, access to education and its connection to the alleviation of poverty, good governance, which are major ingredients in averting crime against women. Today's girl-child education is for her tomorrow's living. Afebendeugne in Ugwu (2001) defines women education as the education that would make a woman become aware of herself and her capacity to exploit her environment, and involves training in literacy and vocational skills to enable her become functional in the society. When maternal care is adequately provided for the girl-child the aims and objectives of education will be achieved.

However, current efforts including national and global programmes have been to target increased enrolment of the girl-child into the different levels of education in Nigeria. The federal government introduced the Universal Basic Education Programme to provide cheap and affordable education to all and sundry. Most if not all the state governments in Nigeria have also introduced free and compulsory primary and secondary schools for both male and female children in various states. Again most state governments have also passed the child rights and protection acts that will eliminate (or at least reduce) the withdrawal of the girl-child from school and to prevent parents or guardians from using their school age children to hawk or do endless labour activities. This is so important because it promotes girl child education which chances nation building.

METHODOLOGY

Research design

This research work is a survey research and is based on administering of interviewing method and questionnaire as instruments for data collection and analysis. The research work is designed to find out the attitude of parents towards their female child education in Gashu'a local Government area of Yobe state. Since the research project, according to Nwana (1980) point out that research design is a term used to describe a number of decisions which needs before the data are collected. Then it is important at this point to state the decisions which need to be taken for collection of data in this research work. The decisions were based on: population, sample and sampling techniques, the instrument to be used for the research work and method of data analysis.

Population of the study

The total number of population is hundred (100), which is the total number of population of the study area. Twenty (20) teachers, fifteen (15) parents, five (5) relatives and ten (10) guardians were also selected for the purpose of the study, making a total of hundred populations.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

In this research work, the sample is carried out in Gashua local Government area of yobe state. The researchers applied random sampling method in selecting the individual involved, which include the teachers, parents, guardians, and other relatives of the girl-child.

Instrumentation

The measuring instrument for this study was the interview and questionnaire. A set of ten (10) questionnaires were simply designed and fifty (50) copies were distributed to the respondents who were all inhabitants of Gashu'a local Government area of Yobe, state. The researchers therefore, adopted and applied: interview and questionnaire.

Administration of the instrument

The interview and questionnaire are the methods were administered to investigate the attitude of parents towards the education of their female children in yobe state. The interview and questionnaires were administered to obtain information from the respondents. The interview was conducted by the researchers, followed by the distribution of the questionnaires with the help of research assistants, who helped in distributing and collecting of the questionnaires from the respondents.

Procedure for data analysis

The questionnaire and interview were administered to investigate the attitudes of parents towards the education of their female child in Yobe state, which is restricted to Gashu'a local Government. Fifteen (15) items in the questionnaires were used for respondents to provide opinion on two options which is "Yes" or "No".

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Presentation and analysis of data

The presentation of data used for the study is in form of tables and percentages. The questionnaire and interview methods were used to obtain the necessary data from Gashu, a local government, particularly parents. The total score of each item was calculated by finding the simple percentage equal to the score of each option over the total number of questionnaire administered.

That is: $\text{Total No. of Respondents} \times 100 /$

$\text{Total No. of Questionnaire}$

The data were classified and tabulated as frequency distribution and simple percentage of all the responses obtained from the questionnaires used in analysing the data.

Parents often see the education of their female children very weak, as they assure that the best place for the work of a female child is in the kitchen.

Table 1.1

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	36	72
No	14	28
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 36 respondents representing 72% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that the education of female child is very weak, as their parents assure that the best place for the work of a female child is in the kitchen, while 14 respondents representing 28% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the education of a female child is not weak. Therefore, majority of the parents of female children are in full support to the education of women, that is, women should be allowed to acquire education which is better than to stay at home, while some parents are of the view that, the education of a female child is not weak. Therefore, majority of the parents of female children are in full support to the education of women, that is, women should be allowed to acquire education which is better than to stay at home, while some parents are of the view that female should stay at home for a home management.

Educational backwardness of women is mainly caused by parents.

Table 1.2

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	31	62
No	19	38
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 31 respondents representing 62% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the educational backwardness of women is mainly caused by parents, while 19 respondents representing 38% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the educational backwardness of women is not mainly caused by parents. This shows that majority of the parents of a female child are of the opinion that, it is true that sometimes it is the parents that mainly caused the educational backwardness of female children while some of the view that, it is not mainly caused by parents but sometime by teachers and administrators.

The education of men is more important than that of women.

Table 1.3

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	26	52
No	24	48
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 26 respondents representing 52% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the education of men is more important than that of women, while 24 respondents representing 48% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the education of men is not more important than that of women. So that in this regard, some relatives of female children are in full support of educating men is more important than educating a woman, while some among them are in support of educating their female children because if they acquire education they will not be ruined by the society.

Is the education of women very important?

Table 1.4

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	31	62
No	19	38
Total	50	100

The total above clearly indicates that, 31 respondents representing 62% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the education of women is very important while 19 respondents representing 38% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, the education of women is not very important. That is, majority of the relatives of female children are in support of the women's educating because it is through the education that a female child can understand herself and feel very safe, whereas some among the relatives of female children do not recognize the importance of female's education because some they think that sometimes if a female child is allowed for a schooling, she may end up learning bad habits.

Does poor parental background lead to women's educational backwardness?

Table 1.5

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	32	64
No	18	36
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicates, 32 respondents representing 64% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, poor parental background may lead to women's educational backwardness, while 18 respondents representing 36% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, poor parental background may not lead to women's educational backwardness. That is to say that, some teachers of a female children are in full support that the educational backwardness of women is sometime caused by poor parental background, while some are of the view that it is not caused by poor parental background but sometime caused by poverty.

Will you agree that poverty contributes to women's educational backwardness?

Table 1.6

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	31	62
No	19	38
Total	50	100

The above table clearly indicate that, 31 respondents representing 62% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, poverty contributes to women's educational backwardness, while 19 respondents representing 38% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, poverty will not contribute to women's educational backwardness. From the above views of the respondents which are the teachers of female children are of the view that poverty is the main factor affecting female child education, while are of the view that is not poverty that contribute to women's educational backwardness but their parents at times.

Lack of enlightenment on the part of parents may lead to women's educational backwardness

Table 1.7

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	37	74
No	13	26
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that 37 respondents representing 74% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, lack of enlightenment on the part of parents may lead to women's educational backwardness while 13 respondents representing 26% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, lack of enlightenment on the part of parents may not lead to women's educational backwardness.

With regard to the above views, we strongly observed and understand that majority among the relatives of female education are in full support that lack of enlightenment on the part of parents may lead to women's educational backwardness, while some are of the view that, it is not the lacking of enlightenment on the part of parents that lead to women's educational backwardness, Parents do not send their daughters to school because of financial problem.

Parents do not realize the importance of women's education

Table 1.8

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	23	46
No	27	54
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 24 respondents representing 48% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, parents do not send their daughters to school because of financial implication, while 26 respondents representing 52% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, is not because of financial implicating that parents do not send their daughters to school. It is shown that some respondents which are the teachers of girl-child are of the view that, poverty contributes to the educational backwardness of women, while some are of the view that, parents do not send their daughters to school because of some of the parents do not realize the importance of female education and the look at their education as something which is useless. If you educate a man you are educating an individual, but if you educate a woman you are educating the whole nation.

Parents see that women's education will end up by learning bad habits, values, norms and attitudes.

Table 1.9

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	33	66
No	17	34
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 33 respondents representing 66% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, if you educate a man you are educating an individual, but if you educate a woman you are educating the whole nation, while 17 respondents representing 34% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, if you educate a woman you are educating the whole nation. Therefore, majority of the respondents which are parent's girl-child are of the view that, the education of women is very important because it may bring about the advancement and the development of the whole nation, while some are of the view that the education of women will not bring about any development to the nation at large.

If you educate a man you are educating an individual, but if you educate a woman you are educating the whole nation.

Are you willing to send your female children to school?

Table 1.10

Choice	Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	32	64
No	18	36
Total	50	100

The table above clearly indicate that, 32 respondents representing 64% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, they are willing to send their female children to school, while 18 respondents representing 36% of the total sample population of the respondents are of the view that, they are not willing to send their female children to school. With regard to these views of parent, majority of them are of the view that they will allow their female children to acquire formal education for self-fulfillment and self-reliance, and the development of the society, while some among the parents are of the view that, they will not allow their female children to attend school because they may end up by learning bad habits, values, norms and attitudes.

VIEWS OF THE RESPONDENTS

The researchers conducted oral interview and from the interview these are the techniques adopted and applied:

In contact with Mohammed Audu, the headmaster of NEAZDP Nursery and primary school Gashu'a, we threw this question to him as follow: is the education of female very important?

He stresses it out that female child education is having great importance more especially to their parents. This is because if a girl had gone to school, she will assist her brothers and sisters with other things and to some extent paid school fees to her juniors which are supposed to be done by parents. In addition to the discussion, he went on by saying

that if a female child has gone to school, the schooling will help her to build the economic progress of her husband and taken proper care of her children.

Another view from Ahmad Abdulra'uf Alheri supermarket Gashu'a, said that in a home where the parents allow their female children to attend school will help the female children and even her husband as well as their children. As an educated mother, she will not deny her children from attending school. She will also know how to take care of their children with the skills, norms and values that she acquired in the school.

In contact with Malam Adamu Shafi'u GSS Gashu'a, we threw this question to him as:

Is the educational backwardness of women mainly caused by parents? He said that in a home where there is no co-operation between the father and the mother on the issue of female child towards school, a conflict, quarrel will take place whereby the female education will generally feel unsafe and maladjusted. Therefore, whenever she goes to school she will be thinking about her parent's conflicts, thus she will not achieve much in the school.

Another view from Mr. Sama'ila Ago zonal office also stress it out that co-operation between the father and mother towards female child education contributes a lot, unlike where there is conflict and quarrel over the female child advocate. He further says that such situations makes the female child unsafe and create an interest on schooling, even if such a child goes to school she will be absent minded hence her academic activities affected.

In contact with Mallam Moh'd Usman of Government Day Secondary School Gashu'a, we threw this question to him as follow: is the education of female harmful to the society?

He stresses it out, where he said that female child education is not harmful, but if the parent cannot afford that, it is better to rush her into marriage in order to avoid her getting ruined by the society.

Mohammed Musa Jinjiri Yobe specialist hospital Gashu'a added that, it is only through education that the female child can support herself and adjust freely comfortable even with her husband.

In contact with Mrs. Hauwa mohammed of Ramat primary school Gashu'a, we threw this question to her as follows: is the education of men more important than that of women?

She answered the question above by saying that nowadays female child render herself as male do feels the same as male. They do even better, therefore, they should be allowed to do what male child can do.

With the above views from parents, we strongly observed that some are in full support to the female child education while some are not in support to it. Despite the fact that some are literate while some are illiterate, it is through this way that the researchers use together their positive and negative views and interest towards female child education in Yobe state which is restricted to Gashu'a local government area.

Majority of the parents of the girl-child are in support to the education of their female children, this is because if a girl had gone to school, she will assist her brothers and sisters with other things and to some extent paid school fees to her junior which is supposed to be done by parents. And also if a female child has gone to school, the schooling will help her to build the economic progress of her husband and taken proper care of her children. Whereas some of the parents are not in full support to it, but it is due to their own outlook on the education of their female children, some are of the view that, in an attempt to educate their daughters, they may end up by learning bad habits, norms, beliefs, values and attitudes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it was established that, the attitude of parents towards girl child education was positive, but still there are some problems like illiteracy of parents, poverty as well as lack of government support that lead to women's educational backwardness. It is also identified that illiterate parents are of determining factor of the Girl child education in schools. Therefore, there is no doubt that the implementation of the recommendations about the parents and their attitude would do a lot to foster the education of girls in Gashu'a local government area of yobe state.

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